

Potentiometric Evaluation of Apparent Fixed Charge Densities on Porous Membranes impregnated with Potassium Cobaltinitrite Precipitate in Presence of Alkali Chloride Solutions

T. SAMANTA and A. S. BASU*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

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Membrane potentials developed across two porous membranes, parchment and cellophane, impregnated with potassium cobaltinitrite precipitate in presence of LiCl, NaCl and KCl over the concentration range $0.0001-0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ have been studied. Potentials show the trend, $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$. The apparent fixed charge densities of the precipitated membranes in presence of these electrolyte solutions have been calculated using the methods of TMS, Kobatake *et al.* and Kamo *et al.* The values are quite agreeable with each other within the limits of experiments.

It has now been well established that porous membranes impregnated with sparingly soluble inorganic salts, simple or complex, develop membrane potentials when these are used to separate an electrolyte solution of different concentrations on the two sides. Some authors have extensively studied these potentials on various artificial porous membranes like parchment, cellophane or sintered glass deposited either with inorganic precipitates or with lipids suggesting that these may act as model membranes to mimic some properties of biological membranes *in vivo*¹⁻¹¹.

The purpose of the present paper is to report the studies on the development of membrane potentials when potassium cobaltinitrite precipitate is used to impregnate either parchment or cellophane separating solutions of different concentrations of an alkali chloride. Attempt have also been made to calculate the apparent fixed charge densities developed within the precipitated membranes in presence of different alkali chloride solutions utilising some classical methods. The reasons for selecting this precipitate is also to find if any preference is developed for K^+ ion, since ion-selective behaviour is observed with sparingly soluble inorganic salts^{1,2,13}.

Experimental

Impregnation of parchment and of cellophane with potassium cobaltinitrite precipitate was done by the method of interaction suggested by Siddiqui *et al.*³ and Beg *et al.*⁹. The parchment and cellophane papers of research grade mainly used for dialysis were cut into circular discs and were

attached to the flanged ends of wide glass tubes (5-6 cm dia) with suitable adhesive like 'Quickfix'. The entrapped air within the pores of the membranes was removed by maintaining a small hydrostatic pressure difference on the two sides of the membranes so that water flow could take place slowly without damaging the pores. Magnetic stirring, both inside and outside, helped to remove the air bubbles adhered to the surface of the membrane. The outside surfaces of the wet membranes, after removing their surface water, were dipped in beakers containing 0.2 M KNO_3 solutions. The freshly prepared sodium cobaltinitrite solution of the same strength was poured inside of the tubes. The arrangements with two different membranes parchment and cellophane were kept for ~72 h, whereafter the sides of the two solutions were interchanged and the systems were kept for about 72 h with fresh solutions. The surfaces of the membranes were found to be coated with yellow precipitates of potassium cobaltinitrite. The membranes were washed thoroughly with deionised water, and the precipitates adhered loosely on the surfaces were smoothly brushed off. Different sets of membranes were prepared, and those showing uniform deposition under microscope were selected for the studies. The membranes were further cut into small circular discs and attached with 'Quickfix' adhesive between the flanged ends of the half-cells of U-shaped tubes. These were not allowed to become dry to avoid any disturbances because of entrapped air. Solutions of LiCl, NaCl and KCl were prepared with deionised water and analytical grade salts. Concentration range used were 0.1×10^{-3} to $500 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ maintaining a constant ratio of 1 : 10 between the successive solutions. The cell was of the usual

type,

where, SCE is the tiny saturated calomel electrode with fine KCl-agar tip. To minimise the osmotic effect and to nullify the hydrostatic pressure difference, the solutions on the two sides of the membrane were maintained at the same level, and were constantly stirred with magnetic stirrer. Potentials were measured with a Cambridge potentiometer having the sensitivity of 0.001 mV connected to a suspended coil galvanometer having current sensitivity 10^{-10} A mm⁻¹. Solutions on the two sides were frequently renewed. Steady potential values were observed within 1–2 h depending upon the concentrations of the solutions from concentrated to dilute range. After the steady potentials were obtained, interchange of the solution on the two sides were made to test the reproducibility of the results and also to find the development of any asymmetry potential. The average value of three or four readings not differing by ± 0.5 mV were recorded. All measurements were made at the temperature $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Results and Discussions

The average of the potential values observed across the two membranes, parchment (P) and cellophane (C) supported potassium cobaltinitrite precipitate separating electrolyte solutions of KCl, NaCl and LiCl within the concentration range $0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 500 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ with $C_1 : C_2 = 1 : 10$ are recorded in Table 1.

The potential values in both the membranes show the order, $K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$ indicating some preference for K^+ , may be due to the presence of potassium ion in the precipitate. However, the values are much lower than the theoretical Nernstian values, 59.1 mV for 1 : 10 ratio. This is obvious since the membranes are porous and these are not true ion-exchange membranes. The deviations become much larger as the concentrated range is approached. It is quite evident that the non-ideal behaviour of the solutions for which activity should be considered instead of concentrations could not improve this situation much. The porosities of these two membranes after precipitation play the most important part. It has now been well established⁸ that for the development of potential across a membrane separated by an electrolyte solution of two concentrations the charge density and the membrane porosities are the most important controlling factors. If the pores are too large any amount of charge on the membrane does not help to produce good potentials; whereas the membranes with very small pores can produce ideal potentials even with small charge density. Comparing the deviations of the recorded values from the theoretical Nernstian value, it seems plausible

that these deviations are mainly due to water transport and the co-ion transfer^{14,15}, the latter phenomenon becomes more prominent towards the concentrated range as will be evident from further calculations of $\bar{i}_-$, the anion transport number in the membrane phase. The performances of both the membranes, parchment (P) and cellophane (C) are more or less alike so far as the potassium cobaltinitrite precipitate is concerned and it seems that porosities outweigh the selectivity.

To study the further characteristics of these precipitated membranes, which are not proper ion-exchange membranes, in presence of different electrolytes, the calculations of the apparent charge densities and the intramembrane mobility ratios of cation and anion may be interesting. It has been established that amongst the various earlier methods for the calculation of apparent fixed charge on the membrane¹⁶⁻¹⁸ the technique based on TMS equation has been found^{5,9,8} to be the most suitable for these types of precipitate membranes. According to the TMS theory¹⁵ the membrane potential, E_m for a uni-univalent electrolyte is given by

$$E_m = \frac{2.303 RT}{F} \left[\log \frac{C_2(4C_1^2 + \bar{X}^2)^{1/2} + \bar{X}}{C_1(4C_2^2 + \bar{X}^2)^{1/2} + \bar{X}} + \bar{U} \log \frac{(4C_2^2 + \bar{X}^2)^{1/2} + \bar{X}\bar{U}}{(4C_1^2 + \bar{X}^2)^{1/2} + \bar{X}\bar{U}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, $\bar{X}$ is the apparent fixed charge densities expressed in mol dm⁻³ of the imbibed water and is assumed to be constant over the range of concentration studied,

$$U = (u - v)/(u + v)$$

where, u and v are the apparent mobilities of cation and anion, respectively, in the membrane. In order to evaluate $\bar{X}$ and u/v of any membrane using TMS equation (1), the following method is adopted.

Assuming a net negative charge of unity ($\bar{X} = -1$), a series of theoretical E_m values across a membrane are calculated for a particular speculated value of u/v over a concentration range but always maintaining a constant ratio between two successive concentrations, say $C_1 : C_2 = 1 : 10$, and are plotted against $\log(1/C_2)$. A family of theoretical curves for different anticipated values of u/v over the same concentration range are thus obtained. The observed membrane potentials given in Table 1 are also plotted on the same Fig. 1 over the range of experimental concentrations. The extent of parallel shift of any experimental curve from a theoretical curve gives the value of $-\log \bar{X}$ and also the value of u/v . The curves of KCl, NaCl and LiCl for the parchment membrane (P) are found to run parallel with the theoretical curves having the u/v values 1.4, 1.0 and 0.9 respectively, and for the cellophane (C) are found to correspond to the values of 1.3, 1.1 and 1.0, respectively. The calcu-

Fig. 1. TMS method of calculating apparent fixed charge densities on precipitate impregnated membranes, parchment (P) and cellophane (C): (O) KCl, (□) NaCl, and (Δ) LiCl.

lated $\bar{X}$ values of the membranes with different electrolytes are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 1—AVERAGE POTENTIALS (mV) ACROSS POTASSIUM COBALTNITRITE PRECIPITATE IMPREGNATED PARCHMENT AND CELLOPHANE MEMBRANES

Concn. ($\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³)		Parchment			Cellophane		
C_2	C_1	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl
1.0	0.1	31.0	23.5	17.0	33.0	23.0	22.5
10	1.0	25.5	21.0	13.0	24.5	16.0	18.5
20	2.0	20.5	16.5	11.0	20.2	13.5	13.0
50	5.0	14.0	12.0	3.5	12.0	6.0	5.5
100	10	10.0	3.5	-1.7	6.8	-2.0	3.0
200	20	5.5	-4.0	-4.5	2.0	-6.5	-2.5
500	50	2.5	-6.0	-8.5	0.5	-7.5	-7.5

Attempts have also been made to calculate the apparent fixed charges of these membranes with the help of the equations of Kobatake *et al.*²⁰, and Kamo *et al.*²¹ for the comparison of the results with those of TMS equations, since these equations have overcome the shortcomings of TMS equation. The Kobatake *et al.* equation for potential of a negatively charged membrane separating a univalent electrolyte of two concentrations, C_1 and C_2 , may be expressed as

$$|E_m| = \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \gamma - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} - 2\alpha \right) \ln \left(\frac{C_2 + \alpha\beta\bar{X}}{C_1 + \alpha\beta\bar{X}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where, $|E_m| = -(F_m F/RT)$ is the reduced form of potential; $\gamma = C_2/C_1$, a constant ratio of concentrations on the two sides throughout the experiment; $\alpha = u/(u+v)$, u and v are the molar mobilities of positive and negative ions, respectively, defined in terms of center of mass fixed frame of reference; β is a characteristic parameter of the membrane structure; and $\bar{X}$ is the charge density (mol dm⁻³) of the membrane. These parameters are assumed to be independent of the external salt concentrations. For the calculations of $\bar{X}$, equation (2) is simplified

in two forms applying the limiting conditions of dilute and concentrated solutions. When the external salt concentrations are dilute ($\bar{X} \gg C_2$), the logarithmic expansion of the above equation may be cut at the first power of C_2 , and by rearrangement is reduced to the form,

$$|E_m| = \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \gamma - \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\alpha\beta\gamma} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} - 2\alpha \right) \frac{C_2}{\bar{X}} + \dots \quad (3)$$

The plots of the values of $|E_m|$ vs C_2 should yield a straight line with intercept equals to $1/\beta \ln \gamma$ giving the value of β and a slope,

$$S_d = \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\alpha\beta\gamma} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} - 2\alpha \right) \cdot \frac{1}{\bar{X}_d}$$

relating α , β and $\bar{X}_d$ (d for the dilute range). For evaluation of α , the second limiting condition of high external salt concentration is imposed and a slightly modified form of the equation is used as follows utilising the apparent transport number of anion within the membrane, $\bar{i}_-$. Kobatake *et al.*²⁰ have shown that $\bar{i}_-$ is related to the measured potential by the equation,

$$|E_m| = (1 - 2\bar{i}_-) \ln \gamma \quad (4)$$

This may be correlated with equation (3) and after rearrangement may be expressed as

$$\bar{i}_- = (1 - \alpha) \left[1 + \frac{(1 + \beta - 2\alpha\beta) \cdot \alpha(\gamma - 1)}{2(1 - \alpha) \ln \gamma} \cdot \frac{\bar{X}}{C_2} \right] \quad (5)$$

Taking the inverse of this relation, $1/\bar{i}_-$, expanding binomially the second term in square parenthesis, neglecting the higher powers of $1/C_2$ on the condition of high external salt concentrations ($\bar{X} \ll C_2$) the following relation is obtained,

$$\frac{1}{\bar{i}_-} = \frac{1}{(1 - \alpha)} + \frac{\alpha(1 + \beta - 2\alpha\beta)(\gamma - 1)}{2(1 - \alpha)^2 \ln \gamma} \cdot \frac{\bar{X}_c}{C_2} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) suggests that the plots of $1/\bar{i}_-$ vs $1/C_2$ should give a straight line with intercept, $1/(1 - \alpha)$ and a slope,

$$S_c = \frac{\alpha(1 + \beta - 2\alpha\beta)(\gamma - 1)}{2(1 - \alpha)^2 \ln \gamma} \cdot \bar{X}_c$$

where a relation of α , β and $\bar{X}_c$ is obtained (the subscript c for concentrated solutions). Calculated values of $\bar{i}_-$ using equation (4) are recorded in Table 2.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the plots of $|E_m|$ vs C_2 , and $1/\bar{i}_-$ vs $1/C_2$ using equations (3) and (6), respectively, for the cellophane membrane only. Maintaining a constant value of $\gamma = C_2/C_1 = 10$, the calculated values of β and S_d , and the values of α and S_c from Figs. 2 and 3 respectively, for the cellophane and from the Figs. (not shown) for the parchment are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2—APPARENT TRANSPORT NUMBER OF ANION, $\bar{t}_-$ WITHIN THE PRECIPITATE IMPREGNATED MEMBRANES*

Concn. ($\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³)		Parchment			Cellophane		
C_2	C_1	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	KCl	NaCl	LiCl
1.0	0.1	0.24	0.30	0.36	0.22	0.30	0.31
10	1.0	0.28	0.32	0.39	0.29	0.37	0.34
20	2.0	0.33	0.36	0.41	0.33	0.39	0.39
50	5.0	0.38	0.40	0.47	0.40	0.45	0.45
100	10	0.42	0.47	0.51	0.44	0.52	0.48
200	20	0.45	0.53	0.54	0.48	0.56	0.52
500	50	0.48	0.55	0.57	0.50	0.56	0.56

*Calculated vide equation (4).

The calculated values of $\bar{X}$ in the forms of $\bar{X}_c$ and $\bar{X}_d$ are tabulated in Table 4 (rows 2, 3 and 6, 7) for both the membranes.

Kamo *et al.*²¹ have further suggested a method for the calculation of thermodynamically effective charge density, $\Phi\bar{X}$ (Φ is the fraction of counter ions in the unbound form) by defining a parameter, P_S , permselectivity expressed by the relation,

$$P = \frac{1 - \bar{t}_- - \alpha}{\alpha - (2\alpha - 1)(1 - \bar{t}_-)} = \frac{1}{(4\xi^2 + 1)^{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

where, $\xi = C/\bar{X}$, C is the mean value of the concentrations on two sides of the membrane. From equation (7) it is seen that when $C = \bar{X}$, $\xi = 1$ and $P_S = 0.447$. Thus the $\Phi\bar{X}$ values are calculated from the plots of P_S vs $\log C$ and the concentrations corresponding to the P_S at 0.447 are calculated. P_S values are calculated utilising the $\bar{t}_-$ and α values of Tables 2 and 3, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the plots

Fig. 2. Plots of $|E_m|$, reduced potentials vs external concentrations, C_2 with precipitate impregnated cellophane membrane by the method of Kobatake equation (3): (O) KCl, (□) NaCl, and (Δ) LiCl.

Fig. 3. Plots of $1/\bar{t}_-$ vs $1/C_2$ of Kobatake equation (6) for precipitate impregnated cellophane membrane: (O) KCl, (□) NaCl, and (Δ) LiCl.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED VALUES OF PARAMETERS, β , S_d AND, α AND S_c *

Membrane	Electrolyte	β	α	S_d	S_c
Parchment	KCl	2.15	0.51	11.07	0.095
	NaCl	2.55	0.42	8.79	0.094
	LiCl	3.67	0.44	9.80	0.018
Cellophane	KCl	2.15	0.48	12.29	0.038
	NaCl	3.19	0.42	9.80	0.020
	LiCl	2.98	0.42	11.34	0.038

*Of Kobatake equations (8) and (6) from Figs. 2 and 3, respectively; S_d = slope at dilute range, S_c = slope at concentrated range.

TABLE 4—CALCULATED VALUES OF THE APPARENT FIXED CHARGE DENSITIES OF PARCHMENT AND CELLOPHANE MEMBRANES IMPREGNATED WITH POTASSIUM COBALTNITRITE PRECIPITATE USING DIFFERENT METHODS

Membrane	Method	$[\bar{X}](\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³)		
		KCl	NaCl	LiCl
Parchment	TMS	0.5	0.9	1.0
	Kobatake, $\bar{X}_c$	0.9	1.0	0.5
	Kobatake, $\bar{X}_d$	3.4	5.1	2.3
	Kamo, $\Phi\bar{X}$	0.4	0.9	0.2
Cellophane	TMS	0.8	0.4	0.4
	Kobatake, $\bar{X}_c$	0.9	0.5	1.1
	Kobatake, $\bar{X}_d$	3.6	3.3	3.1
	Kamo, $\Phi\bar{X}$	0.6	0.4	0.3

of P_S vs $\log C$ of cellophane membrane only. Calculated values of $\Phi\bar{X}$ of both the membranes with different electrolytes are shown in Table 4.

Fig. 4. Plots of ψ vs $\log C$ with precipitate impregnated cellophane membrane for calculation of $\phi\bar{X}$, the thermodynamic effective charge density by method of Kamo equation (7): (O) KOI, (□) NaOI, and (Δ) LiOI.

Comparisons of the different values of $\bar{X}$ calculated by different classical equations (Table 4) show some interesting results. In spite of the differences in the arguments and in method of derivations of these equations, the values of $\bar{X}$, the apparent charge density in both the membranes, are more or less of the same order. The values, however, differ to some extent in the magnitude in different methods amongst the various ions. In Kobatake equation (2), $\bar{X}$ has been assumed to be constant over the concentration range, and $\bar{X}_d$ and $\bar{X}_c$ should have the more or less the same values. In this case the calculated $\bar{X}_d$'s are found to have much higher values than those of $\bar{X}_c$'s. The plausible reasons may be that the proper limiting conditions for the validity of Kobatake equation in the dilute range, viz. $\bar{X}_d \gg C_s$ could not be maintained because of the unsatisfactory behaviour of the membranes beyond the dilute range used here. However, for $\bar{X}_c$'s the values are more or less quite agreeable with those of TMS and of Kamo. This suggests that in spite of the various limitations of the TMS equation the charge densities may be calculated with this equation at least for qualitative comparison between the various precipitated membranes in presence of different electrolytes.

The differences between $\bar{X}_d$ and $\bar{X}_c$ values may also be to some extent due to the nature of co-ion and water transfer at the two limiting conditions for this type of porous membrane. It may be mentioned that Siddiqi *et al.*⁶ found quite different values for

$\bar{X}_d$ and $\bar{X}_c$ with their parchment supported barium phosphate membrane. Beg *et al.*⁸, however, found almost equal values of $\bar{X}_d$ and $\bar{X}_c$ with their parchment supported CoS and NiS precipitates. The calculated values of $\phi\bar{X}$, the thermodynamic effective charge density by the method of Kamo *et al.*²¹, are quite agreeable with those of other methods within experimental errors. Recently, Chakravarty *et al.*²² have suggested a method for the calculation of effective charge of a membrane using the technique of electroosmotic flow, and have shown that the values more or less agree with those of the classical methods.

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